

TWO-PHASE SAMPLING WITH CALIBRATION WEIGHT ADJUSTMENT IN SMALL-AREA AREA ESTIMATION FOR LONGITUDINAL SURVEYS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16366887>

Abstract: Accurate estimation of population parameters in small area estimation (SAE) is crucial, particularly in double sampling, where non-response can introduce significant bias. Although traditional estimators have been widely used to improve estimation accuracy, they often fail to fully adjust for non-response bias in small domains. This study proposes a new calibration-based estimator that extends the framework of an existing estimator by incorporating a Kullback-Leibler distance function to adjust the design weights. The estimators are derived under two conditions: (1) non-response affecting only the study variable and (2) non-response affecting both the study and auxiliary variables. This study evaluates the estimator's performance using real-life data from the HFCS and the IHS in Nigeria (2019-2021), analyzing three distinct time periods: before, during, and after COVID-19. The MSE analysis results confirm that the proposed estimator consistently outperforms traditional SAE estimators, particularly in high non-response scenarios. The findings of this study suggest that integrating calibration techniques into double sampling frameworks significantly enhances estimation efficiency. The proposed calibration estimator is a robust and computationally feasible approach for improving domain mean estimation in longitudinal surveys, particularly when non-response rates are high. This study demonstrates superior efficiency and reliability in two-phase sampling under stratified random sampling by comparing the proposed estimator with existing methods.

Keywords: Calibration, small area estimation, sub-sampling, non-response, Kullback-Leibler distance measure, mean square error.

1. Introduction

Reliable population characteristics estimation is crucial in survey research, particularly when direct estimates are unreliable due to small sample sizes and non-response. Double sampling, also known as two-phase sampling, has been widely used to improve estimation efficiency by incorporating auxiliary information and subsampling non-respondents (Hansen & Hurwitz, 1946). In small area estimation (SAE), double sampling helps to reduce bias and variance by drawing a second-phase sample from the dataset, which includes the sub-sampled element and adjusting for the non-respondents data, where sample sizes within certain domains are

insufficient and the parameter of the auxiliary variable is unknown. This technique is particularly relevant in longitudinal surveys, where maintaining data accuracy over multiple waves is challenging due to unit non-response and attrition (Iseh & Bassey, 2021). This study was motivated by the demand for more precise and less biased estimators in two-phase sampling, as traditional estimators struggle with the limitations of incomplete responses and sub-optimal weighting adjustments (Khare et al., 2021).

Several researchers have explored double sampling estimation techniques to address the challenges of small sample sizes and non-response. Hansen and Hurwitz (1946) introduced an unbiased estimator that subsamples non-respondents to improve estimation accuracy. Later, Tikkiwal and Ghiya (2000) extended this approach by developing direct ratio estimators for stratified sampling. Anekeya et al. (2018) further improved upon these estimators by incorporating nonlinear cost functions to optimize sample allocation in two-phase domain estimation. However, these methods often fail to account for optimal weight adjustments, making them inefficient when the non-response rates are high. In addition, many existing estimators assume complete auxiliary information, which is rarely the case in real-world surveys (Ashutosh, 2021). These limitations emphasize the need for a more robust calibration-based estimator that effectively handles non-response bias and variance reduction in double sampling frameworks.

The effective adjustment of design weights to compensate for nonresponse bias and sampling variability is a major challenge in double sampling for small area estimation. Many existing methods rely on basic weighting adjustments that do not fully utilize auxiliary information to enhance estimator efficiency. Bias and mean square error (MSE) minimization remain critical concerns in two-phase estimation, particularly when domain sample sizes are small or zero (Clement & Enang, 2015). Furthermore, the impact of nonresponse on efficiency loss is often overlooked, leading to unreliable estimates in small domains (Iseh & Enang, 2021; Iseh & Bassey, 2022a, 2022b; Ikot & Iseh, 2024). To address these gaps, this study introduces a new calibration-based estimator that minimizes the Kullback-Leibler distance function between design and calibration weights, thereby improving the precision of domain mean estimation while maintaining robustness under various nonresponse scenarios.

This study extends the estimator proposed by Hansen and Hurwitz (1946) by incorporating calibration techniques into a double sampling framework for domain estimation in longitudinal surveys. The proposed estimator refines weighting adjustments using auxiliary variables to ensure better control over bias and variance. This study derives theoretical expressions for bias and mean square error and validates the estimator through empirical studies of real-world household survey data from the Central Bank of Nigeria.

2. Sample Design

Consider a finite population U under study of size N divided into D domains; $U_1, U_2, U_3, \dots, U_D$ of sizes; $N_1, N_2, N_3, \dots, N_D$ respectively. Let $Y^{(t)}$ be the study variable with population mean $\bar{Y}_d^{(t)}$ and $X^{(t)}$ the auxiliary variable with mean $\bar{X}_d^{(t)}$. Let $y_{dh}^{(t)}$ and $x_{dh}^{(t)}$ ($h = 1, 2, \dots, H$) be the observations on the h^{th} stratum in the population for the variables $Y^{(t)}$ and $X^{(t)}$ respectively. We assume that non-response is observed on the study variable $Y^{(t)}$ and not on the auxiliary variable $X^{(t)}$ in the first case. Both $Y^{(t)}$ and $X^{(t)}$ are affected by non-response in the second case. The population means $\bar{X}_d^{(t)}$ of the auxiliary variable $X^{(t)}$ is unknown. We first estimate $\bar{X}_d^{(t)}$ using principles of double sampling and then use the estimate to obtain the estimate of $\bar{Y}_d^{(t)}$. In this case, a large preliminary sample of size n'_{dh} is selected from the population of N units using Simple Random Sampling without Replacement (SRSWOR) scheme at the first phase. Information on $X^{(t)}$ is obtained from all

n'_{dh} units and use to estimate $\bar{X}_d^{(t)}$. A second subsample of size n_{dh} units ($n_{dh} < n'_{dh}$) is selected from the first phase sample units by SRSWOR in the second phase. Information from $Y^{(t)}$ is obtained at the second phase by subsampling the non-respondents. During the first phase, out of n'_{dh} units, n'_{dh1} units respond while n'_{dh2} units do not respond on the auxiliary variable $X^{(t)}$. Hansen and Hurwitz (1946) suggested drawing a subsample of size $r_{dh2} = \frac{n_{dh2}}{g}$, where $g \geq 1$ is predetermined, from then $n_{dh2} = n_{dh} - n_{dh1}$ non-respondents and eliciting responses from all of them. Domains may be quite large or small. For a typical d^{th} domain U_d several characteristics may be defined to include the domain total, mean, variance, and even covariance.

$$Y_{U_d} = \sum_{U_d} y_{dg}, \quad \bar{Y}_{U_d} = \frac{1}{N_d} \sum_{U_d} y_{dg}, \quad S_{U_d}^2(Y) = \frac{1}{N_d - 1} \sum_{g \in U_d} (y_{dg} - \bar{Y}_{U_d})^2 \quad \text{and}$$

$$C_{U_d}(X, Y) = \frac{1}{N_d - 1} \sum_{g \in U_d} (x_{dg} - \bar{X}_{U_d})(y_{dg} - \bar{Y}_{U_d}) \quad \text{respectively.}$$

2.1 Existing Estimators under Double Sampling

There exist some domain estimators for population mean in the double sampling technique with a single auxiliary variable in the presence of non-response.

Hansen and Hurwitz’s (1946) Estimator

First, we consider the Hansen and Hurwitz (1946) unbiased estimator under single-stage sampling as follows:

$$\hat{\bar{y}}_d = \sum_{h=1}^H W_{dh} \bar{y}_{dh}^* \tag{1}$$

where $\bar{y}_{dh}^* = \frac{n_{d1} \bar{y}_{d1} + n_{d2} \bar{y}_{d2}}{n_d}$

and

$$V(\hat{\bar{y}}_d) = \sum_{h=1}^H \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_d} \right) W_{dh}^2 S_{y_{dh1}}^2 + \sum_{h=1}^H \frac{K_{dh} - 1}{n_{dh2}} W_{dh}^2 W_{dh2} S_{y_{dh2}}^2 \tag{2}$$

where $S_{y_{dh1}}^2$ and $S_{y_{dh2}}^2$ are the mean square of the entire group and non-response group, respectively, of the study variable in the population for the h^{th} stratum,

and

$W_{dh} = \frac{N_{dh}}{N_d}$ is the response rate of the d domain in the h^{th} stratum .

$W_{dh2} = \frac{N_{dh2}}{N_d}$ is the rate of non-response of the d domain in the h^{th} stratum .

Anekeya et al. (2018)

Following the techniques of Hansen and Hurwitz (1946), Anekeya et al. (2018) proposed unbiased estimators for estimating domain mean using double sampling with a nonlinear cost function in the presence of nonresponse. The unbiased estimator for estimating the domain population mean using $(n_{d1} + r_{d2})$ observations on y_{d1} domain study character is given by

$$\bar{y}_d = \frac{n_{d1}}{n_d} \bar{y}_{d1} + \frac{n_{d2}}{n_d} \bar{y}_{rd2} = w_{d1} \bar{y}_{d1} + w_{d2} \bar{y}_{rd2}$$

Similarly, the estimate for the domain auxiliary variable is given as follows:

$$\bar{x}_d = \frac{n_{d1}}{n_d} \bar{x}_{d1} + \frac{n_{d2}}{n_d} \bar{x}_{rd2} = w_{d1} \bar{x}_{d1} + w_{d2} \bar{x}_{rd2}$$

where \bar{y}_d and \bar{x}_d are the sample domain means for the observation y_{di} and x_{di} respectively.

They proposed two ratio estimators; \hat{Y}_{dR1} and \hat{Y}_{dR2} thus:

$$\hat{Y}_{dR1} = \frac{\bar{y}_d}{\bar{x}_d} \bar{x}'_d \tag{3}$$

$$\hat{Y}_{dR_2} = \frac{\bar{y}_d}{\bar{x}_d} \bar{x}_d \tag{4}$$

Bias of the Ratio Estimator \hat{Y}_{dR_1}

The bias and mean square error of the ratio estimator \hat{Y}_{dR_1} is given, respectively, as

$$\text{Bias}(\hat{Y}_{dR_1}) = \bar{Y}_d \left(\frac{1}{n_d} - \frac{1}{n'_d} \right) C_{xd} (C_{xd} - \rho_{xdy_d} C_{yd}) + \left(\frac{K_{d_1}-1}{n_d} \right) W_{d_2} C_{xd_2} (C_{xd_2} - \rho_{xd_2y_{d_2}} C_{yd_2}) \tag{5}$$

$$\text{MSE}(\hat{Y}_{dR_1}) = \left[\left(\frac{1}{n'_d} - \frac{1}{N_d} \right) S_{y_d}^2 + \left(\frac{1}{n_d} - \frac{1}{n'_d} \right) S_{dR_1}^2 - \left(\frac{K_{d_1}-1}{n_d} \right) W_{d_2} S_{dR_2}^2 \right] \tag{6}$$

(6)

where $S_{dR_1}^2 = S_{y_d}^2 + S_{x_d}^2 R_d^2 - 2\rho_{xdy_d} R_d S_{x_d} S_{y_d}$

$$S_{dR_2}^2 = S_{y_{d_2}}^2 + S_{x_{d_2}}^2 R_d^2 - 2\rho_{xd_2y_{d_2}} R_d S_{x_{d_2}} S_{y_{d_2}} \quad \text{and } R_d = \frac{\bar{Y}_d}{\bar{X}_d}$$

Similarly, the bias and mean square error of the ratio estimator \hat{Y}_{dR_2} is given, respectively, as

$$\text{Bias}(\hat{Y}_{dR_2}) = \bar{Y}_d \left(\frac{1}{n_d} - \frac{1}{n'_d} \right) \left(\rho_{xdy_d} \frac{S_{x_d} S_{y_d}}{\bar{X}_d \bar{Y}_d} \right) + \left(\frac{K_{d_1}-1}{n_d} \right) W_{d_2} \rho_{xd_2y_{d_2}} \frac{S_{x_{d_2}} S_{y_{d_2}}}{\bar{X}_d \bar{Y}_d} \tag{7}$$

where $C_{xd} = \frac{S_{x_d}}{\bar{X}_d}$, $C_{yd} = \frac{S_{y_d}}{\bar{Y}_d}$, $C_{xd_2} = \frac{S_{x_{d_2}}}{\bar{X}_d}$, $C_{yd_2} = \frac{S_{y_{d_2}}}{\bar{Y}_d}$

$$\text{MSE}(\hat{Y}_{dR_2}) = \left[\left(\frac{1}{n'_d} - \frac{1}{N_d} \right) S_{y_d}^2 + \left(\frac{1}{n_d} - \frac{1}{n'_d} \right) S_{dR_1}'^2 + \left(\frac{K_{d_1}-1}{n_d} \right) W_{d_2} S_{dR_2}'^2 \right] \tag{8}$$

(8)

where $S_{dR_1}'^2 = S_{y_d}^2 + S_{x_d}^2 R_d^2 + 2\rho_{xdy_d} R_d S_{x_d} S_{y_d}$

$$S_{dR_2}'^2 = S_{y_{d_2}}^2 + S_{x_{d_2}}^2 R_d^2 + 2\rho_{xd_2y_{d_2}} R_d S_{x_{d_2}} S_{y_{d_2}}$$

n'_d = Domain size in the second phase, and

K_{d_1} = inverse sampling rate

3. Proposed Estimator

Motivated by Hansen and Hurwitz (1946), as shown in Eq. 1, the proposed longitudinal estimator is defined as follows:

$$\hat{Y}_{Dc} = \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^{*(t)} \bar{y}_{dh}^{*(t)} \tag{9}$$

The proposed longitudinal estimator in Eq. 9 is calibrated under two conditions:

Condition 1: The study variable is influenced by non-response but the auxiliary variable is free from non-response.

Condition 2: The study and auxiliary variables are not free from non-response.

Here, the Kullback distance measure is used to minimize the distance between the stratum weights W_{dh} and the calibration weights $W_{dh}^{*(t)}$ subject to the constraints under conditions 1 and 2.

Proposed Estimator under Condition 1:

Given the Kullback Distance Function (φ) as

$$\varphi = \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^{*(t)} \log \left(\frac{W_{dh}^{*(t)}}{W_{dh} q_{dh}} \right) - W_{dh}^{*(t)} - W_{dh}$$

subject to constraints

$$\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^{*(t)} \bar{x}_{dh}^{(t)} = \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}'_{dh} \tag{10}$$

$$\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^{*(t)} S_{dh}^{2(t)} = \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} \tag{11}$$

where

$$\bar{x}'_{dh}(t) = \frac{1}{n'_{dh}} \sum_{h=1}^{n'_{dh}} x'_{dh}(t)$$

Hence, the optimization problem is given as follows:

$$L_1 = \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^{*(t)} \log\left(\frac{W_{dh}^{*(t)}}{W_{dh} q_{dh}}\right) - W_{dh}^{*(t)} - W_{dh} - T_1 \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^{*(t)} \bar{x}_{dh}(t) - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}'_{dh}(t) \right] - T_2 \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^{*(t)} S_{dh}^{2(t)} - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} \right]$$

Taking the partial derivative of L_1 with respect to $W_{dh}^{*(t)}$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial L_1}{\partial W_{dh}^{*(t)}} &= W_{dh}^{*(t)} \frac{W_{dh} q_{dh}}{W_{dh}^{*(t)}} \frac{1}{W_{dh} q_{dh}} + \log\left(\frac{W_{dh}^{*(t)}}{W_{dh} q_{dh}}\right) - 1 - T_1 \bar{x}_{dh}(t) - T_2 S_{dh}^{2(t)} = 0 \\ \Rightarrow W_{dh}^{*(t)} &= W_{dh} q_{dh} \left[1 + T_1 \bar{x}_{dh}(t) + T_2 S_{dh}^{2(t)} \right] \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Substituting $W_{dh}^{*(t)}$ in Eqs. 10 and 11 and solving for T_1 and T_2 gives

$$\begin{aligned} T_1 &= \frac{\left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}'_{dh}(t) - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}(t)\right) \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{dh}^{4(t)}\right) - \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{dh}^{2(t)}\right) \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}(t) S_{dh}^{2(t)}\right)}{\left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}^2(t)\right) \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{dh}^{4(t)}\right) - \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}(t) S_{dh}^{2(t)}\right]^2} \\ T_2 &= \frac{\left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}^2(t)\right) \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{dh}^{2(t)}\right) - \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}(t) S_{dh}^{2(t)}\right) \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}'_{dh}(t) - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}(t)\right)}{\left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}^2(t)\right) \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{dh}^{4(t)}\right) - \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}(t) S_{dh}^{2(t)}\right]^2} \end{aligned}$$

Then, Eq. 9 is given as follows:

$$\hat{y}_{DC1}^t = \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{y}_{dh}^{*(t)} + \beta_1 \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}'_{dh}(t) - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}(t) \right) + \beta_2 \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{dh}^{2(t)} \right) \tag{13}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_1 &= \frac{\left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}'_{dh}(t) - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}(t)\right) \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{dh}^{4(t)}\right) - \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{dh}^{2(t)}\right) \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}(t) S_{dh}^{2(t)}\right)}{\left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}^2(t)\right) \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{dh}^{4(t)}\right) - \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}(t) S_{dh}^{2(t)}\right]^2} \\ \beta_2 &= \frac{\left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}^2(t)\right) \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{dh}^{2(t)}\right) - \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}(t) S_{dh}^{2(t)}\right) \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}'_{dh}(t) - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}(t)\right)}{\left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}^2(t)\right) \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{dh}^{4(t)}\right) - \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{x}_{dh}(t) S_{dh}^{2(t)}\right]^2} \end{aligned}$$

Derivation of the MSE under Condition 1

The proposed estimator is assumed to be asymptotically unbiased; hence, the MSE is derived using the following large sample approximations:

$$\text{Let } e_0^* = \frac{\bar{y}_{dh}^{*(t)} - \bar{y}_{dh}(t)}{\bar{y}_{dh}(t)}, \quad e_1 = \frac{\bar{x}'_{dh}(t) - \bar{x}_{dh}(t)}{\bar{x}_{dh}(t)}, \quad e_2 = \frac{\bar{x}_{dh}(t) - \bar{X}_{dh}(t)}{\bar{x}_{dh}(t)}, \quad e_3 = \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} - S_{x_{dh}}^2(t)}{S_{x_{dh}}^2(t)},$$

$$\text{where } \bar{y}_{dh}^{*(t)} = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^{n_{dh}} y_{dh}^{*(t)}}{n_{dh}}, \quad \bar{x}'_{dh}(t) = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^{n'_{dh}} x'_{dh}(t)}{n'_{dh}}, \quad \bar{x}_{dh}(t) = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^{n_{dh}} x_{dh}(t)}{n_{dh}}, \quad \bar{X}_{dh}(t) = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^L \bar{x}_{dh}(t)}{N_d}, \quad S_{x_{dh}}^2 = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^{n_{dh}} (x_{dh}(t) - \bar{x}_{dh}(t))^2}{n_{dh} - 1}$$

$$\text{and } S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^{n_{dh}} (x_{dh}^{(t)} - \bar{x}_{dh}(t))^2}{N_{dh} - 1}, \quad \bar{X}_{dh}(t) = \frac{\sum_d^N \bar{x}_{dh}(t)}{N}$$

$$\begin{cases} \bar{y}_{dh}^{*(t)} = \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}(1 + e_0^*) \\ \bar{x}'_{dh}(t) = \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)}(1 + e_1) \\ \bar{x}_{dh}(t) = \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)}(1 + e_2) \\ S_d^{2(t)} = S_{dh}^{2(t)}(1 + e_3) \end{cases}$$

Again, let

$$E[e_0^*] = E\left[\frac{\bar{y}_{dh}^{*(t)} - \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}}{\bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}}\right] = \frac{\bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} - \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}}{\bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} = 0$$

Similarly, $E[e_1] = E[e_2] = E[e_3] = 0$

Also,

$$E[e_1^2] = \frac{1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)}} \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}}\right) S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} \quad E[e_2^2] = \frac{E[\bar{x}'_{dh}(t) - \bar{x}_{dh}(t)]^2}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)}} = \frac{Var(\bar{x}'_{dh}(t))}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)}} = \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}}\right) \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)}}$$

$$E[e_0^{2*}] = \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}}\right) \frac{S_{y_{dh}}^{2(t)}}{\bar{Y}_{dh}^{2(t)}} + \frac{K_{dh}-1}{\bar{Y}_{dh}^{2(t)} n_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{y_{dh}}^2 \quad E[e_3^2] = \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}}\right) (\lambda_{04} - 1)$$

$$E[e_0^* e_1] = \frac{S_{xy_{dh}}^{(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}}\right) = \frac{1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}}\right) \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)}$$

$$E[e_0^* e_2] = \frac{S_{xy_{dh}}^{(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}}\right) = \frac{1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}}\right) \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)}$$

$$E[e_1 e_2] = \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}}\right) \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)}}, \quad E[e_0^* e_3] = \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}}\right) C_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} \lambda_{12} = \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}}\right) \frac{S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)}}{\bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \lambda_{12}$$

$$E[e_1 e_3] = \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}}\right) C_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} \lambda_{03} = \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}}\right) \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)}} \lambda_{03}$$

$$E[e_2 e_3] = \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}}\right) C_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} \lambda_{03} = \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}}\right) \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)}} \lambda_{03}$$

Therefore, the mean square error is given as follows:

$$\mathbf{MSE}(\hat{y}_{Dc1}^{(t)}) = E(\hat{y}_{Dc1}^{(t)} - \bar{Y}_d^{(t)})^2 \tag{14}$$

Eq. 13 can be written in terms of the large sample approximation as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{y}_{Dc1}^{(t)} &= \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}(1 + e_0^*) + \beta_1 \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)}(1 + e_1) - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)}(1 + e_2) \right] \\ &\quad + \beta_2 \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)}(1 + e_3) \right] \\ &= \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} + \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} e_0^* + \beta_1 \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} e_1 - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} e_2 \right] \\ &\quad - \beta_2 \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} e_3 \right] \end{aligned}$$

Hence, Eq. 14 becomes

$$\mathbf{MSE}(\hat{y}_{Dc1}^{(t)}) = E\left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} e_0^* + \beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} e_1 - \beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} e_2 - \beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} e_3\right]^2$$

$$= \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{Y}_{dh}^{2(t)} E(e_0^{2*}) + 2\beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} E(e_1 e_0^*) - 2\beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} E(e_2 e_0^*) - \right. \\ \left. 2\beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} E(e_3 e_0^*) + \beta_1^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)} E(e_1^2) - 2\beta_1^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)} E(e_1 e_2) - \right. \\ \left. \beta_1 \beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} E(e_3 e_1) + \beta_1^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)} E(e_2^2) + 2\beta_1 \beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} E(e_3 e_2) + \right. \\ \left. \beta_2^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{4(t)} E(e_3^2) \right]$$

Substituting for large sample approximations gives

$$= \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{Y}_{dh}^{2(t)} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{y_{dh}}^{2(t)}}{\bar{Y}_{dh}^{2(t)}} + \frac{K_{dh}-1}{\bar{Y}_{dh}^{2(t)} n_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{y_{dh}}^2 \right\} + 2\beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \left\{ \frac{1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} \right\} - 2\beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \left\{ \frac{1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} \right\} - \\ 2\beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)}}{\bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \lambda_{12} \right\} + \beta_1^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)} \left\{ \frac{1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)}} \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} \right\} - \\ 2\beta_1^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)}} \right\} - \beta_1 \beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)}} \lambda_{03} \right\} + \\ \beta_1^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh}^2 \left\{ \frac{1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)}} \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} \right\} + 2\beta_1 \beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)}} \right\} + \\ \beta_2^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{4(t)} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) (\lambda_{04} - 1) \right\} \right]$$

$$\text{Let } M_1 = \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right), M_2 = - \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{n_{dh}} \right) = \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{n'_{dh}} \right)$$

Then

$$MSE(\hat{y}_{DC1}^{(t)}) = \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ M_1 S_{y_{dh}}^{2(t)} + \frac{K_{dh}-1}{n_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{y_{dh}}^2 \right\} - 2\beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 M_2 \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} - \right. \\ \left. 2\beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} M_1 S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} \lambda_{12} + \beta_1^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 M_2 S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} - \beta_1 \beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 M_1 S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} \lambda_{03} + \right. \\ \left. 2\beta_1 \beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 M_2 S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} + \beta_2^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{4(t)} M_1 (\lambda_{04} - 1) \right] \tag{15}$$

To obtain the minimum MSE, is partially differentiated with respect to β_1 and β_2 respectively as

$$2\beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 M_2 S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} - \beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} (M_1 \lambda_{03} - 2M_2) = \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 M_2 \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)}$$

and

$$\beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} (2M_2 - M_1 \lambda_{03}) + 2\beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{4(t)} M_1 (\lambda_{04} - 1) = 2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} M_1 S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} \lambda_{12}$$

solving for β_1 and β_2 simultaneously gives

$$\beta_{1OPT} = \left\{ \frac{\left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 M_2 \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} \right) \left(2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{4(t)} M_1 (\lambda_{04} - 1) \right)}{- \left(2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} M_1 S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} \lambda_{12} \right) \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} (M_1 \lambda_{03} - 2M_2) \right)} \right\}$$

$$\beta_{2OPT} = \left\{ \frac{- \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} (2M_2 - M_1 \lambda_{03}) \right) \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 M_2 \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} \right)}{\left(2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 M_2 S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} \right) \left(2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{4(t)} M_1 (\lambda_{04} - 1) \right)} \right\}$$

Substituting for β_{1OPT} and β_{2OPT} in Eq.15 gives

$$\begin{aligned}
 MSE_{min}(\hat{y}_{Dc1}^{(t)}) &= \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) S_{y_{dh}}^{2(t)} + \frac{K_{dh}-1}{n_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{y_{dh2}}^2 \right\} - 2\beta_{1OPT} \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \right. \right. \\
 &\left. \left. \frac{1}{n_{dh}} \right) \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} - 2\beta_{2OPT} \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} \lambda_{12} + \beta_{1OPT}^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{n_{dh}} \right) S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} - \right. \\
 &\left. \beta_{1OPT} \beta_{2OPT} \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} \lambda_{03} + 2\beta_{1OPT} \beta_{2OPT} \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{n_{dh}} \right) S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} + \right. \\
 &\left. \beta_{2OPT}^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{4(t)} \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) (\lambda_{04} - 1) \right] \tag{16}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proposed Estimator under Condition 2

To obtain the properties of the proposed estimator when non-response is observed in both the study and the auxiliary variables, condition 2 is considered.

Since there is a non-response in the auxiliary variable, we consider the following:

$$\bar{x}_{dh}^{*(t)} = \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} (1 + e_2^*) \text{ and } \bar{x}'_{dh}{}^{*(t)} = \bar{X}'_{dh}{}^{(t)} (1 + e_1^*)$$

So that

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned}
 E[e_0^{2*}] &= \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{y_{dh}}^{2(t)}}{\bar{Y}_{dh}^{2(t)}} + \frac{K_{dh}-1}{\bar{Y}_{dh}^{2(t)} n_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{y_{dh2}}^2 \\
 E[e_1^{2*}] &= \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)}} + \frac{K'_{dh}-1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)} n'_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^2 \\
 E[e_2^{2*}] &= \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)}} + \frac{K_{dh}-1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)} n_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^2 \\
 E[e_3^2] &= \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) (\lambda_{04} - 1) \\
 E[e_0^* e_1^*] &= \frac{1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} + \left(\frac{K'_{dh}-1}{n'_{dh2}} \right) W_{dh2} \frac{S_{x_{dh2}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh2}}^{(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \\
 E[e_0^* e_2^*] &= \frac{1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} + \left(\frac{K_{dh}-1}{n_{dh2}} \right) W_{dh2} \frac{S_{x_{dh2}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh2}}^{(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \\
 E[e_0^* e_3] &= \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)}}{\bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \lambda_{12} \\
 E[e_1^* e_2^*] &= \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)}} + \frac{K'_{dh}-1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)} n'_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^2 \\
 E[e_1^* e_3] &= \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)}} \lambda_{03} \\
 E[e_2^* e_3] &= \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)}}
 \end{aligned} \right. \tag{17}$$

Substituting Eq.17 into Eq.13 gives

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{y}_{Dc}^{(t)} &= \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} (1 + e_0^*) + \beta_1 (1 + e_4) \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} (1 + e_1^*) - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{X}'_{dh}{}^{(t)} (1 + e_2^*) \right] + \beta_2 (1 + \\
 &e_5) \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} (1 + e_3) \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} + \beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} e_1^* - \beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} e_2^* + \beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} e_1^* e_4 - \beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} e_2^* e_4 - \beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} e_3 - \beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} e_3 e_5 \tag{18}$$

Such that

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MSE}(\hat{y}_{Dc2}^{(t)}) &= E[\hat{y}_{Dc2}^{(t)} - \bar{Y}_d^{(t)}]^2 \\ &= \left\{ \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} + \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} e_0^* + \beta_1(1 + e_4) \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} e_1^* - \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} e_2^* \right] - \beta_2(1 + e_5) \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} e_3 - \bar{Y}_d^{(t)} \right] \right\}^2 \\ &= \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{Y}_{dh}^{2(t)} E(e_0^{2*}) + 2\beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} E(e_1^* e_0^*) - 2\beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} E(e_2^* e_0^*) - 2\beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} E(e_3 e_0^*) + \beta_1^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)} E(e_1^{2*}) - 2\beta_1^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} E(e_1^* e_2) - \beta_1 \beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} E(e_1^* e_3) + \beta_1^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh}^2 E(e_2^2) + 2\beta_1 \beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} E(e_3 e_2) + \beta_2^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^4 E(e_3^2) \right] \tag{19} \end{aligned}$$

Substituting Eq.17 into Eq.19 gives

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{Y}_{dh}^{2(t)} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{y_{dh}}^{2(t)}}{\bar{Y}_{dh}^{2(t)}} + \frac{K_{dh}-1}{\bar{Y}_{dh}^{2(t)} n_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{y_{dh2}}^2 \right\} + 2\beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \left\{ \frac{1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} + \left(\frac{K'_{dh}-1}{n'_{dh2}} \right) W_{dh2} \frac{S_{x_{dh2}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh2}}^{(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \right\} - 2\beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \left\{ \frac{1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} + \left(\frac{K_{dh}-1}{n_{dh2}} \right) W_{dh2} \frac{S_{x_{dh2}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh2}}^{(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \right\} - 2\beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)}}{\bar{Y}_{dh}^{(t)}} \lambda_{12} \right\} + \beta_1^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)}} + \frac{K'_{dh}-1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)} n'_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^2 \right\} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)}} + \frac{K'_{dh}-1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)} n'_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^2 \right\} - 2\beta_1^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)}} + \frac{K'_{dh}-1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)} n'_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^2 \right\} - \beta_1 \beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)}} \lambda_{03} \right\} + \beta_1^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)}} + \frac{K_{dh}-1}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{2(t)} n_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^2 \right\} + 2\beta_1 \beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \bar{X}_{dh} S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \frac{S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)}}{\bar{X}_{dh}^{(t)}} \right\} + \beta_2^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^4 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) (\lambda_{04} - 1) \right\} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MSE}(\hat{y}_{Dc2}^{(t)}) &= \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) S_{y_{dh}}^{2(t)} + \frac{K_{dh}-1}{n_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{y_{dh2}}^2 \right\} + 2\beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} + \left(\frac{K'_{dh}-1}{n'_{dh2}} \right) W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh2}}^{(t)} \right\} - 2\beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} + \left(\frac{K_{dh}-1}{n_{dh2}} \right) W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh2}}^{(t)} \right\} - 2\beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{y_{dh}}^{3(t)} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \lambda_{12} \right\} + \beta_1^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} + \frac{K'_{dh}-1}{n'_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^2 \right\} - 2\beta_1^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} + \frac{K'_{dh}-1}{n'_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^2 \right\} - \beta_1 \beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} \lambda_{03} \right\} + \beta_1^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} + \frac{K_{dh}-1}{n_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^2 \right\} + 2\beta_1 \beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} \right\} + \end{aligned}$$

$$\beta_2^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{4(t)} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) (\lambda_{04} - 1) \right\} \quad (20)$$

To obtain the minimum MSE, is partially differentiated with respect to β_1 and β_2 respectively as

$$\begin{aligned} & -2\beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ M_2 S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} + f_1 W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^2 \right\} + 2\beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ M_1 S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} + M_2 S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} \lambda_{03} \right\} = \\ & -2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ M_2 \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} + f_1 W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh2}}^{(t)} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

and

$$-\beta_1 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 M_2 S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} \lambda_{03} - 2\beta_2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{4(t)} \{M_1 (\lambda_{04} - 1)\} = 2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{y_{dh}}^{3(t)} \{M_1 \lambda_{12}\} \quad (22)$$

where $M_1 = \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right)$, $M_2 = - \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{n_{dh}} \right) = \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{n'_{dh}} \right)$, and $f_1 = \left(\frac{K_{dh}-1}{n_{dh2}} - \frac{K'_{dh}-1}{n'_{dh2}} \right)$

Solving for β_1 and β_2 simultaneously in Eqs. 21 and 22

$$\beta_{1OPT} = \left\{ \frac{\left(-2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ M_2 \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} + f_1 W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh2}}^{(t)} \right\} \right) \left(-2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{4(t)} \{M_1 (\lambda_{04} - 1)\} \right)}{- \left(2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{y_{dh}}^{3(t)} \{M_1 \lambda_{12}\} \right) \left(2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ M_1 S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} + M_2 S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} \lambda_{03} \right\} \right)} \right\}$$

$$\beta_{2OPT} = \left\{ \frac{\left(-2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ M_2 S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} + f_1 W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^2 \right\} \right) \left(2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{y_{dh}}^{3(t)} \{M_1 \lambda_{12}\} \right)}{- \left(\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 M_2 S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} \lambda_{03} \right) \left(2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ M_2 \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} + f_1 W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh2}}^{(t)} \right\} \right)} \right\}$$

Substituting for β_{1OPT} and β_{2OPT} in Eq. 20 gives

$$\begin{aligned} MSE_{min}(\hat{y}_{DC2}^{(t)}) = & \left[\sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) S_{y_{dh}}^{2(t)} + \frac{K_{dh}-1}{n_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{y_{dh2}}^2 \right\} + 2\beta_{1opt} \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \right. \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. \frac{1}{n_{dh}} \right) \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} + \left(\frac{K'_{dh}-1}{n'_{dh2}} \right) W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh2}}^{(t)} \right\} - 2\beta_{1opt} \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \rho_{xy_{dh}} S_{x_{dh}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh}}^{(t)} + \right. \\ & \left. \left(\frac{K_{dh}-1}{n_{dh2}} \right) W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^{(t)} S_{y_{dh2}}^{(t)} \right\} - 2\beta_{2opt} \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{y_{dh}}^{3(t)} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) \lambda_{12} \right\} + \beta_{1opt}^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{n_{dh}} \right) S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} + \right. \\ & \left. \frac{K'_{dh}-1}{n'_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^2 \right\} - 2\beta_{1opt}^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \frac{1}{n_{dh}} \right) S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} + \frac{K'_{dh}-1}{n'_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^2 \right\} - \beta_{1opt} \beta_{2opt} \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n'_{dh}} - \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. \frac{1}{n_{dh}} \right) S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} \lambda_{03} \right\} + \beta_{1opt}^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) S_{x_{dh}}^{2(t)} + \frac{K_{dh}-1}{n_{dh2}} W_{dh2} S_{x_{dh2}}^2 \right\} + 2\beta_{1opt} \beta_{2opt} \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. \frac{1}{n_{dh}} \right) S_{x_{dh}}^{3(t)} \right\} + \beta_{2opt}^2 \sum_{h=1}^L W_{dh}^2 S_{x_{dh}}^{4(t)} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{n_{dh}} - \frac{1}{N_{dh}} \right) (\lambda_{04} - 1) \right\} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

4. Empirical Study

Real-life data obtained from the Department of Statistics of the Central Bank of Nigeria for the Household Finances and Consumption Survey (HFCS) and the Integrated Household Survey (IHS), which is a quarterly survey, are partitioned into WAVE 1, 3, and 4 for 2019 (before COVID-19), WAVE 1, 2, 3, and 4 for 2020 (during COVID-19), and WAVE 2, 3, and 4 for 2021 (after COVID-19). The population comprises selected households spread across the 37 states (domains) of Nigeria. Again, the population is subdivided into five groups (strata) of those working in government organizations, private organizations, self-employed with employees, self-employed without employees, and unpaid family workers.

4.1 Performance of Estimators by Empirical Investigation

The performance of the existing and proposed estimators is presented in Tables 1, 2, and 3 using the mean square errors, and Tables 4, 5, and 6 using the percent relative efficiency (PRE).

Table 1: Estimator performance using variance and MSE in 2019

ESTIMATORS	WAVE 1	WAVE 3	WAVE 4
$V(\hat{y}_d)$	56748543	59284324	84364734
$MSE(\hat{Y}_{DR1})$	74638584	24375473	58457486
$MSE(\hat{Y}_{DR2})$	84457585	74548594	78595644
$MSE_{min}(\hat{Y}_{Dc1}^{(t)})$	756545	678982	759485
$MSE_{min}(\hat{Y}_{Dc2}^{(t)})$	8550533	7544380	7333293

Table 2: Estimator performance using variance and MSE in 2020

ESTIMATORS	WAVE 1	WAVE 2	WAVE 3	WAVE 4
$V(\hat{y}_d)$	56876955	67586958	45784854	74589485
$MSE(\hat{Y}_{DR1})$	26768766	19565054	28548584	34574850
$MSE(\hat{Y}_{DR2})$	43747384	54584853	35475849	24747844
$MSE_{min}(\hat{Y}_{Dc1}^{(t)})$	400830	439433	548495	546443
$MSE_{min}(\hat{Y}_{Dc2}^{(t)})$	7233839	8574754	7233638	6595043

Table 3: Performance of estimators using variance and MSE in 2021

ESTIMATORS	WAVE 2	WAVE 3	WAVE 4
$V(\hat{y}_d)$	2264743	3236372	2463734
$MSE(\hat{Y}_{DR1})$	5495459	4384838	5465746
$MSE(\hat{Y}_{DR2})$	4484859	6505859	6595784
$MSE_{min}(\hat{Y}_{Dc1}^{(t)})$	34733	43473	56474.12
$MSE_{min}(\hat{Y}_{Dc2}^{(t)})$	547585	658683	735467

Table 4: Percent Relative Efficiency of the Existing and Proposed Estimators in 2019

ESTIMATORS	WAVE 1	WAVE 3	WAVE 4
\hat{y}_d	100	100	100
\hat{Y}_{DR1}	67.19	79.52	107.34
\hat{Y}_{DR2}	7501.01	8731.34	11108.14
$\hat{Y}_{Dc1}^{(t)}$	663.68	785.80	1150.43
$\hat{Y}_{Dc2}^{(t)}$	67.19	79.52	107.34

Table 5: Percent Relative Efficiency of the Existing and Proposed Estimators in 2020

ESTIMATORS	WAVE 1	WAVE 2	WAVE 3	WAVE 4
\hat{y}_d	100	100	100	100
\hat{Y}_{DR1}	212.47	345.44	160.37	215.73
\hat{Y}_{DR2}	130.01	123.81	129.05	301.39
$\hat{y}_{Dc1}^{(t)}$	14189.79	15380.49	8347.36	13649.99
$\hat{y}_{Dc2}^{(t)}$	786.26	788.20	632.94	1130.99

Table 6: Percent Relative Efficiency of the Existing and Proposed Estimators in 2021

ESTIMATORS	WAVE 2	WAVE 3	WAVE 4
\hat{y}_d	100	100	100
\hat{Y}_{DR1}	242.65	73.80	45.07
\hat{Y}_{DR2}	50.49	49.74	37.35
$\hat{y}_{Dc1}^{(t)}$	6520.36	7444.51	4362.58
$\hat{y}_{Dc2}^{(t)}$	413.58	491.33	334.98

5. Discussion

This discussion is based on the empirical analysis conducted and presented in Tables 1-3. From the results of Tables 1-3, it is observed that the proposed estimators $\hat{y}_{Dc1}^{(t)}$ and $\hat{y}_{Dc2}^{(t)}$ outperformed the existing estimators \hat{y}_d, \hat{Y}_{DR1} and \hat{Y}_{DR2} with smaller MSE in all domains. However, the proposed estimator under condition 1, $\hat{y}_{Dc1}^{(t)}$, has performed more efficiently than that of condition 2, $\hat{y}_{Dc2}^{(t)}$, probably as a result of non-response measured in both the study and auxiliary variables under condition 2 in the domains of the study. This agrees with the result in the literature by Anekeya et al. (2018), that the presence of non-response in both the study and auxiliary variables reduces the performance of the estimators compared to when non-response is only recorded in the study variable. Tables 4, 5, and 6 indicate the relative percentage efficiency of the proposed and existing estimators. The results from the tables indicate that the proposed estimators outperformed the existing estimators in terms of efficiency gains.

6. Conclusion

This study addresses the challenge of SAE under double sampling, particularly in the presence of non-response. Two new calibration-based estimators are developed by extending the Hansen & Hurwitz (1946) estimator, incorporating the Kullback-Leibler distance function to adjust design weights and improve estimation precision. The proposed estimators are expressed under two key conditions: (1) when non-response affects only the study variable and (2) when non-response affects both the study and auxiliary variables.

Theoretical derivations for mean square error confirmed that the proposed estimators significantly reduce error by sub-sampling the non-respondents, thereby improving efficiency compared to existing methods. In addition, empirical validation using Household Finance & Consumption Survey (HFCS) and Integrated House Survey (IHS) data from Nigeria (2019-2021) demonstrate that the estimators consistently outperformed the traditional SAE estimators, particularly in high non-response scenarios. However, it should be noted that gains in

efficiency were relatively high when non-response affected only the study variable than when it was measured on both auxiliary and study variables.

Findings from the empirical study also indicate that the calibration-based adjustment significantly improves domain mean estimation in double sampling. The proposed estimators are computationally feasible and robust, making them effective tools for handling non-response data in longitudinal surveys.

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